

EFFECT OF CORE MATERIALS ON COMPRESSION AFTER IMPACT STRENGTH OF COMPOSITE SANDWICH PANELS SUBJECT TO LOW VELOCITY IMPACT DAMAGE

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents a comparison of the behaviour and performance of composite sandwich panels with different types of cores in terms of compression after impact (CAI) strength following barely visible impact damage (BVID). Two of the most widely used core types, i.e. Nomex honeycomb and PVC foam, are selected to manufacture testing samples, to which low-velocity impacts are applied at low energy levels. Flash thermography is chosen as the preferred NDT technique to carry out both quality control of the sandwich coupons and also impact damage detection. Static CAI tests are performed according to well-established standards. Comparisons between the two core types demonstrate that the Nomex honeycomb core is more efficient at concealing damage at the low impact energies associated with BVID exhibiting both smaller dent depths and delamination area than the PVC foam. The PVC foam core however is of much higher density than the Nomex honeycomb and shows higher levels of both bare compressive and CAI strength. When the relative weight of the cores is taken into consideration, it is the Nomex honeycomb which exhibited better mechanical properties per unit mass.

1 INTRODUCTION

The bending rigidity of a structure can be greatly increased through use of the sandwich structure, by which an entire fuselage could be constructed without any internal stringers, saving significant mass. In comparison with monolithic structures of the same overall thickness as the sandwich skins, the sandwich would have 300 times the flexural stiffness of its monolithic counterpart when the core thickness is 20 times the face sheet thickness. The sandwich panels are also beneficial in terms of heat insulation, sound abatement, fire proofing and vibration damping.

Impact damage has been and continues to be a major issue for aircraft operators, both civilian and military, in terms of loss of revenue for the former (flight delays and cancellations) and loss of capability for the latter. Coupled with the fact that detection of low velocity impacts is generally considered to be more difficult when composite structures are affected, the case for understanding the effect of these impacts and for designing damage tolerant composite structures has clearly been made. Sandwich structures of particular core types are more susceptible to impact damage than monolithic counterparts and that for these reasons historical usage has tended to be limited to secondary structures. One potential reason is that the face sheets, which effectively protect the delicate core material, are generally much thinner than for an equivalent monolithic panel and as such will sustain damage at lower energy level impacts [1-4].

This paper aims to compare the behaviour and performance of composite sandwich panels with two different core materials, which are foam and honeycomb, in terms of compression after impact (CAI) strength following barely visible impact damage (BVID). To fulfil this aim the research work develops a repeatable experimental procedure including manufacturing, impact testing, NDT and CAI testing and analysis of the results obtained.

2 EXPERIMENTAL TESTS

2.1 Sample preparation

The face sheets were firstly laid up using HexPly AS7/8552 carbon fibre/epoxy prepreg with a stacking sequence of [45/-45/90/0]_s and cured in an autoclave under controlled temperature and pressure as 180°C and 7 bar, respectively. They were cut into two equal size sections prior to assembling with layers of FM94 epoxy film adhesive and 5 mm honeycomb and 5 mm foam core materials. The assembled sandwich structures were then bonded in the autoclave using the cure cycle specified in the FM94 technical data sheet. Before the sandwich panels were cut into individual 150mm x 100mm coupons, the edges of the panels required trimming since following the manufacturing processes the panel and face sheet ends were no longer true and square. It was for this reason that it was not possible to produce the maximum of nine perfectly sized coupons from each panel. Finally, 6 coupons for each core types were obtained. Coupons that were not of the standard 150mm x 100mm size would not be compatible with the fixture used to secure the specimen during CAI testing and therefore would be used for additional impacts to identify the BVID energy levels.

Following manufacture, it was necessary to perform a baseline non-destructive inspection of the specimen to detect flaws or defects which may exist prior to indentation or impact testing. This would ensure that any damage discovered following impact testing could be attributed to the impact alone. Flash thermography was used to carry out both quality control of the sandwich coupons and also impact damage detection, mainly due to the fact that the C-scan equipment required specimens to be immersed in fluid during testing, causing the potential risk for water ingress to alter the mechanical properties of the sandwich coupons.

Each test coupon was therefore interrogated using the department flash thermography equipment and the results analysed to ensure no flaws were present. The process is described in more detail during section 2.3. Essentially for each coupon a number of pixels were selected in the middle of the specimen and then logarithmic temperature-time plots were created to ensure that these points were all cooling at a similar rate. The visual images were also studied to ensure uniform colouring of the specimen throughout the testing period – flaws would be visible by localised changes in colours or hot spots. All of the coupons manufactured were quality controlled using this method and all were found to have no flaws present, proving that the manufacturing process was sound and that any damage detected post-impact would be solely attributable to the impact itself.

2.2 Impact testing

Impact testing of specimens was carried out in accordance with ASTM D7766 [5] (Standard Practice for Damage Resistance Testing of Sandwich Constructions). The equipment used was the Rosand Type 5 Instrumented Falling Weight Impact Tester. The standard 16mm diameter hemispherical impactor was used accordingly. During testing the coupons were simply supported and secured using 4 clamps such that the coupon was impacted in its geometric centre. In order to ensure that each coupon was impacted centrally during each test, one of the coupons was marked with its centre point, positioned in the test fixture with the impactor tip just above it and then secured in place with the clamps. White labels were then used to mark the test fixture such that all coupons could be secured in this position during subsequent impacts. The impact energy level was set by varying the height at which the impact carriage was dropped onto the coupon and this was determined by the controller unit and computer software.

2.3 Damage measurement

The main aim of the thermographic testing was to determine the extent of the planar area of delamination (PAD) in the impacted face sheets of the sandwich coupons however first it was necessary to understand the flaws that were being detected and ensure they were in line with what was expected. It was known from the research carried out that flaws, such as delamination, would create a thermal discontinuity in the face sheets of the coupon i.e. the thermo-physical properties would be altered compared to the undamaged areas affecting the diffusion of heat through the thickness of the material. These thermal discontinuities would represent themselves as hot spots on the infrared camera

images. Thermographic analysis of the impacted specimens was, as far as possible, carried out in accordance with the procedures specified in ASTM E2582-07 [6].

The flash thermography equipment divided into two parts: the acquisition system and the analysis software. The acquisition system consisted of the infrared camera/detector, the flash lamp and a computer unit to connect the two together. The purpose of the computer was to synchronize the flash and the camera such that the flash was always triggered during a specific frame of the recording. The camera used was a SC7000 series forward looking infrared camera which detected in the long wave infrared spectral band (7.7 - 9.3 μm). It contained a fan-cooled mercury cadmium telluride detector with a resolution of 320 x 256 pixels. The analysis software allowed the IR camera signal sequences to be retrieved and then replayed in either real time or frame-by-frame. The software also allowed the logarithmic temperature-time plot to be viewed at individual pixel level. For the analysis software the MOSAIQ 4.0 programme was utilised. Throughout all the testing carried out, the sampling rate was set at 50Hz over a 20 second sampling period resulting in 1000 frames of data per test. An internal trigger set the flash to operate at frame 10 of the recording as the ASTM standard specifies at least one frame of data acquisition prior to the flash and 100 frames afterwards also successfully achieved.

The co-ordinate measurement machine (CMM) of Rennishaw Cyclone 3D Scanning System was used to produce the digitised topography of each impact dent by measuring the three dimensional co-ordinates of the coupon surfaces over a specified area. The CMM is a compressed air powered contact measuring system in which a small 7mm diameter sphere is passed along the surface to be scanned recording the depth at a pre-set frequency. The output produced by the CMM was the X, Y and Z co-ordinates of the surface in a 3D data point cloud file. The CMM was adjusted to scan an area 100mm x 60mm to cover the full size of dent topography. Once the 3D data cloud was imported into Microsoft Excel, the information was interrogated and the lowest vertical (Z co-ordinate) point was determined. By noting the X co-ordinate at which the lowest Z co-ordinate occurred, a profile of the surface was then created by plotting the Z co-ordinates across the corresponding Y-axis section. All plots were made on graphs of equal scale such that the surface dent topography could be more easily and fairly compared between coupons.

2.4 Compression after impact testing

The final part of the testing phase was to determine the residual strength of the impacted specimens compared to those that were left undamaged. To facilitate this, the procedure as identified in ASTM C364 – 16 Standard Test Method for Edgewise Compressive Strength of Sandwich Constructions (ASTM 2016) [7] was followed as far as possible. The Avery 600kN hydraulic test machine was used to provide the crushing force necessary to rupture the sandwich coupons. This was connected to a Si-Plan Digital Servo Controller and Data Acquisition Unit Model 879 which controlled the force applied and the rate of displacement of the coupon. The Si-Plan was set to collect the force and displacement data at 5 Hz which is the minimum sampling rate as specified in ASTM C364 (recommended between 5 and 10 per second). It is also recommended to collect around 300 data points per test with this work achieving an average of approximately 800. The data recorded was exported to Microsoft Excel for manipulation in the standard CSV format.

The coupons were held in place with a jig such that the force from the Avery machine could be applied onto the coupons without any eccentricity. Integrated into the jig and located along the longitudinal (150mm) boundaries were four knife edge supports (KES) acting as an anti-buckling device and designed to prevent the coupon from failing through global buckling. However, in order to allow the coupon to be compressed these KES were terminated 15mm from the top of the coupon.

Before proceeding with the test the controller unit was set up to deliver a constant head displacement rate of 1mm/min. Once the test started, the coupons were loaded until 'rupture', which was identified as being the point in testing where the deformation of the coupon was suddenly prominent across its entire width and was always immediately preceded by a distinct and loud cracking noise as well as sudden and significant reduction in the applied load. Following rupture, images were taken of the coupons in their final failed state whilst still in the test jig in order to illustrate the nature of the final deformation before the load was released and the coupon relaxed. If coupons fail during CAI testing where the failure point was within one specimen-thickness of the end-

clamps, i.e. 7mm, the testing results had to be categorized as invalid, namely, ‘gage’, because stress concentrations imparted by the action of the KES had led to premature failure of the ‘gage’ coupons.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Comparison of the performance between the honeycomb and foam sandwich panels along with the analysis of any relationships between dent depth, area of delamination, CAI strength and impact energy were implemented. The aims of this research included some investigation into the relationships between several parameters and a particularly interesting association was that between dent depth and PAD. Impact energy levels were selected as 5J and 10J for impact tests and following CAI. In addition, the samples with non-standard size were tested at energy levels between the 5J and 10J test points, i.e. 6.67J and 8.34J and a lowest possible energy level – 4.25J for impact tests only. Clearly only a limited amount of evidence was available and so a relationship, if any at all, could only be confirmed at the low energy levels tested.

Figure 1 (a) shows the area of delamination against the impact energy for both core types of sandwich panels, where the honeycomb cored sandwich coupons outperformed their foam counterparts at every energy level tested however, this outperformance diminished with increasing energy level, as with which dent depth is in exactly the same manner, see Fig. 1 (b). In particular, at low energy level, both PAD and dent depth of the honeycomb panels exhibit less than 50% of the foam panels, which corroborates with the elastic nature of the honeycomb core which would store impact energy, mainly through core crushing, allowing the face sheet to spring back and hence exhibit little indentation damage and less than these of foam for an equivalent energy level. Figure 1 also indicates a strong linear relationship between surface and sub-surface damage for both core types across the range of impact energy tested. It appeared however that as impact energy increased to the limits of those tested the results seemed to diverge somewhat from the linear lines of best fit. In fact the honeycomb core held the stronger linear link with the foam core demonstrating more scatter at higher impact energy.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1: Comparison of impact damage for sandwich coupons (a) PAD; (b) dent depth.

When CAI strength was normalized by the corresponding undamaged coupon values it was clearly seen from Fig. 2 that the sandwich coupon results show residual strengths much higher than the 70% predicted from the previously reported results. The lines of best fit does not consider the results from 'gage' failures as ASTM C364 [7] decrees that this data should be to be noted as 'invalid'. For the honeycomb coupons this has the effect of shifting the line of best fit higher, even more so as the result from the 10J coupon looks spuriously high. It is considered therefore that a more accurate value for the residual strength would have been approximately 85-87%. The line of best fit for the foam coupons looks more accurate since it passes through what looks like two consistent results at the 10J energy level. However, the result at 5J coupon looks spurious as it represents zero loss in strength for an impact which creates significant delamination damage. It is therefore possible that the line of best fit for the foam sandwiches is also slightly too high and as such the residual strength at BVID threshold could have been slightly lower than the 96% calculated.

Since the two core types were not of comparable density and structural efficiency is a key performance indicator, the compressive failure stress at their respective BVID energy level and divided by the density to give the PVC foam a structural efficiency of 2.66 MNm/kg and the Nomex honeycomb 3.31 MNm/kg. So whilst the honeycomb sandwich would, it is an obvious choice for the structural designer in terms of keeping the component mass low – an inevitable trade-off for the chief engineer to manage between detectability and structural efficiency.

Figure 2: CAI strength of sandwich coupons

An interesting point of note was that the foam coupons exhibited better CAI strength, whereas they showed the opposite way in PAD and dent depth in comparison with the honeycomb coupons. This disagrees with some previous established knowledge that since PAD in the impacted face sheets had a direct and deleterious effect on CAI strength it would make sense that the effect would be stronger on foam core type. Therefore it may be concluded that core type must play an equally significant role during CAI testing to that of existing PAD in the impacted face sheet. The damage tolerance of a sandwich structure was not simply related to how resistant its face sheets were to sustaining impact delaminations but also to the reaction of the core during compression in resisting face sheet delamination buckling.

Figure 3: Edge view of post-compressive failure.

Apart from the residual strength, it would be interesting to carry out some analysis of the failure modes of coupons and investigate any comparisons between core types. The failure mode in the impacted specimens was considered to be most likely that of face sheet delamination buckling, while the undamaged specimens failed by a combination of core compression and core shear failure. Figure 3 shows edge view post-compressive failure of the honeycomb coupon subject to 5J impact after CAI testing and once removed from the test fixture and allowed to relax – it is representative of the images of all impact damaged coupons. As can be seen, the impacted face sheet buckled outwards at a point further away from the loaded end and closer to the impact location than the undamaged face sheet. Core crushing (of around 1mm) was evident and is visible approximately 20mm either side of the point at which the impacted face sheets buckled. Skin-core de-bonding was also observed just beneath

the area of face sheet delamination buckling, suggesting the impact damage could initiate the separation of the skin and core.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The research into the area of composite sandwich construction was carried out by developing an experimental procedure to test sandwich coupons for CAI strength with BVID and making comparisons of the behaviour between two different core types.

The results indicated that, utilising the metric of dent depth, that honeycomb panels demonstrated much better performance in terms of concealing the sub-surface damage by creating smaller indentations than foam cores, which would make the work of the maintenance technician more difficult. Although the foam core showed about 10% higher levels of CAI strength, it however was of much higher density than the Nomex honeycomb. When the relative weight of the cores was taken into consideration, it was the Nomex honeycomb which exhibited better mechanical properties per unit mass.

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